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Synthesis, Characterization and Fluorometric Sensing of 2, 3-diphenylethynyl-meso-tetraphenylporphyrin (H₂TPP(PE)₂) and its Zn (II)-Metal Derivatives

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Abstract

This study focuses on the synthesis, characterization, and fluorometric sensing of 2,3-diphenylethynyl-meso-tetraphenylporphyrin (H₂TPP(PE)₂) and its zinc (II) metal derivatives. The synthesized compounds were obtained through a series of chemical transformations starting from meso-tetraphenylporphyrin, which included bromination, reduction, palladium-catalysed coupling and metalation with Zn (II). The resulting porphyrins were characterized using UV-Visible spectroscopy, proton nuclear magnetic resonance (¹H NMR), high-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS), and other techniques to confirm their structures. The UV-Vis absorption spectra revealed a bathochromic shift in the Soret and Q bands with increasing substitution, particularly for the H₂TPP(PE)₂ and its Zn (II) derivative, indicating the influence of electron-withdrawing substituents. Furthermore, these porphyrins demonstrated promising fluorometric sensing properties, particularly in the detection of cyanide (CN⁻) ions, exhibiting significant spectral changes upon interaction. This study underscores the potential of these modified porphyrins as effective materials for environmental pollutant detection and highlights their utility in optoelectronic and sensor applications. The findings pave the way for further development of these compounds as candidate materials for advanced environmental monitoring and other technological applications.

Keywords: Fluorometric sensing; Porphyrin derivatives; Zinc (II) metalloporphyrin; Environmental pollutant detection; Regioselective substitution

Introduction

The intensifying issue of environmental pollution has placed significant emphasis on the development of sustainable technologies and strategies aimed at minimizing environmental impact and safeguarding ecological balance for present and future generations (Mehraban Khaledi et al., 2024). The dramatic increase in global population, urbanization, and industrialization has led to the widespread release of hazardous pollutants into natural ecosystems (Gheyhani et al., 2020; Yousefnia et al., 2021). Among these, cyanide is a particularly dangerous pollutant due to its high toxicity and extensive industrial use in gold mining, electroplating, and chemical synthesis (Jaszczak et al., 2017; Vaca-Escobar et al., 2024). Even at trace levels, cyanide can severely disrupt aquatic ecosystems and pose serious risks to human health.

Cyanide contamination in water bodies is especially concerning, as it can lead to acute toxicity in aquatic organisms and bioaccumulation in food chains. Traditional detection methods such as ion chromatography and electrochemical analysis, while accurate, are often costly, time-consuming,

and unsuitable for rapid or on-site monitoring. This has driven the need for simple, selective, and sensitive detection systems that can provide real-time results and visual cues for cyanide presence. One class of advanced materials showing significant promise in environmental remediation is porous organic polymers (POPs). These are synthesized by polymerizing organic monomers into three-dimensional frameworks, characterized by high surface areas, thermal stability, tunable pore sizes, and excellent chemical resilience (Yousefnia et al., 2021). Among them, porphyrin-based POPs (Py-POPs), which incorporate porphyrin units into the polymeric backbone, have garnered substantial interest. These materials not only inherit the desirable attributes of POPs but also exhibit unique optoelectronic and coordination properties due to the intrinsic characteristics of porphyrins (Tahoun et al., 2021; Zhou et al., 2021; Maldonado Carmona et al., 2021).

Porphyrins are macrocyclic compounds composed of four pyrrole subunits linked via methine bridges, forming an 18- π -electron conjugated aromatic system (Kim et al., 2022). Their planar structures enable coordination with a variety of metal ions, resulting in metalloporphyrins that play pivotal roles in biological processes such as oxygen transport (e.g., haemoglobin), photosynthesis (e.g., chlorophyll), and redox reactions (Kadish et al., 2010; Liang et al., 2021). The term "porphyrin" is etymologically derived from the Greek word for "purple," reflecting the distinct coloration of many naturally occurring porphyrin complexes (Milroy, 1918; Sheldon, 1994).

Historically, the structural elucidation and synthesis of porphyrins have been key milestones in organic chemistry. Hans Fischer's synthesis of hemin in 1929 and subsequent Nobel Prize in 1930 solidified the foundational role of porphyrins in both natural and synthetic chemistry (Fischer and Zeile, 1929). Since then, extensive research has explored their structural variants, coordination chemistry, photophysical behavior, and functional applications (Lash et al., 2010; Fliegl et al., 2021; Casademont Reig et al., 2021).

Porphyrins are particularly notable for their modularity. They can be synthetically modified at the meso- and β -positions to tailor their physicochemical and electronic properties (Tian et al., 2019; Silvestri et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2021). Various synthetic methods such as the Rothmund (1935), Adler et al. (1964) and Lindsey (1987) approaches have been developed to facilitate the efficient construction of these macrocycles under diverse conditions (Adler et al., 1967; Lindsey, 1994).

Beyond their biological relevance, porphyrins and metalloporphyrins have found applications in a wide array of technological domains. Their photophysical characteristics make them ideal photosensitizers in dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSCs), while their redox activity supports use in catalysis and environmental remediation (Di Carlo et al., 2019; Gao et al., 2022). They are also extensively studied for photodynamic therapy (PDT) in cancer treatment due to their ability to generate reactive oxygen species upon light activation (Yuan et al., 2018; Diaz et al., 2021).

In materials science, porphyrins serve as building blocks for molecular sensors, nonlinear optical (NLO) materials, and porous frameworks capable of selective gas adsorption and photocatalysis (Senge et al., 2007; Zhang et al., 2020). Their conjugated systems allow for high electron delocalization and stability, while the ability to coordinate diverse metal ions enhances their functional versatility (Kumar et al., 2015). The convergence of porphyrin chemistry and polymer science has led to the emergence of porphyrin-based POPs, which harness the benefits of both components. These hybrid materials exhibit remarkable potential in water purification, CO₂ capture, photocatalysis, energy conversion, and biomedical applications, owing to their tunable architecture, robustness, and functional adaptability (Negut et al., 2020; Qi et al., 2020; Ramasamy et al., 2022).

The main goal of this study is to synthesize, characterize, and explore the colorimetric sensing properties of 2,3-diphenylethynyl-meso-tetraphenylporphyrin (H₂TPP(PE)₂) and its zinc (II) derivatives, with a specific focus on cyanide ion detection. By examining their structural and optoelectronic characteristics, this research aims to evaluate the potential of these porphyrin-based compounds as efficient and selective sensors for cyanide in aqueous environments. This focused approach contributes to the development of practical sensing materials for environmental monitoring and public safety.

Materials and Methods

Materials and Reagents

All reagents and solvents were of analytical grade and used without further purification unless stated otherwise. Benzaldehyde, potassium carbonate (K₂CO₃), N-bromosuccinimide (NBS), and

zinc (II) acetate dihydrate $[\text{Zn}(\text{OAc})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ were obtained from SRL. Pyrrole and tributyl(phenylethenyl)stannane were sourced from Sigma-Aldrich. Propionic acid, chloroform, methanol, hexane, anhydrous sodium sulfate, sodium chloride, concentrated sulfuric acid, ammonia solution, sodium bicarbonate, and dimethylformamide (DMF) were purchased from Rankem and Hi-Media. NBS was recrystallized from hot water and dried under vacuum at 65 °C for 6 h prior to use. All solvents were distilled before use. Silica gel TLC plates and column-grade silica (mesh 100–200) were used for chromatographic purification.

Instrumentation

UV-Visible absorption spectra were recorded on a PerkinElmer Lambda 365 spectrophotometer using CH_2Cl_2 as solvent. Proton nuclear magnetic resonance (^1H NMR) spectra were acquired on a Bruker AVANCE 500 MHz NMR spectrometer using CDCl_3 as solvent. High-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) data were obtained using an electrospray ionization mass spectrometer (Bruker Daltonics microTOF).

Synthesis Procedures

Step	Procedure	Reagents & Solvents	Conditions	Product	Yield
1	Synthesis of meso-Tetraphenylporphyrin (H_2TPP)	Benzaldehyde (7.31 mL, 0.072 mol), Pyrrole (5 mL, 0.072 mol), Propionic acid (300 mL)	Reflux for 35 min, silica gel column chromatography, recrystallization from $\text{CHCl}_3/\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$	H_2TPP	19%
2	Metallation to form Cu (TPP)	H_2TPP (1 g, 1.63 mmol), Cupric acetate monohydrate (3.23 g, 16.1 mmol), Methanol (2 mL)	Reflux in CHCl_3 (300 mL) for 1 h, column chromatography ($\text{CHCl}_3/\text{hexane}$, 1:1)	Cu (TPP)	80–85%
3	Nitration to form Cu ($\text{NO}_2\text{-TPP}$)	Cu (TPP) (850 mg, 1.25 mmol), Copper (II) nitrate (0.36 g, 1.25 mmol), Acetic acid (18 mL), Acetic anhydride (65 mL)	Reflux at 80°C for 2 h, silica chromatography ($\text{CHCl}_3/\text{hexane}$, 2:3)	Cu ($\text{NO}_2\text{-TPP}$)	60%
4	Demetallation to form $\text{H}_2(\text{NO}_2\text{-TPP})$	Cu ($\text{NO}_2\text{-TPP}$) (1 g, 1.47 mmol), Concentrated H_2SO_4 , Ammonia	Stir under ice cooling, neutralize with ammonia, extract, column chromatography ($\text{CHCl}_3/\text{hexane}$, 2:3)	$\text{H}_2(\text{NO}_2\text{-TPP})$	70%
5	Bromination to form $\text{H}_2\text{TPP}(\text{NO}_2)\text{Br}_2$	$\text{H}_2(\text{NO}_2\text{-TPP})$ (220 mg, 0.34 mmol), NBS (160 mg, 0.85 mmol), CHCl_3 (50 mL)	Reflux under argon at 78–84°C for 96 h, column chromatography, recrystallization	$\text{H}_2\text{TPP}(\text{NO}_2)\text{Br}_2$	86%
6	Reduction and Deactivation to form $\text{H}_2\text{TPP}(\text{Br})_2$	$\text{H}_2\text{TPP}(\text{NO}_2)\text{Br}_2$ (200 mg, 0.24 mmol), NaBH_4 (16 mg, 0.42 mmol), THF (12 mL), DCM	Reduce in dry THF under argon at 0°C, wash, column chromatography, recrystallization	$\text{H}_2\text{TPP}(\text{Br})_2$	95%
7	Pd-Catalyzed Coupling to form $\text{H}_2\text{TPP}(\text{PE})_2$	$\text{H}_2\text{TPP}(\text{Br})_2$ (200 mg, 0.259 mmol), Pd (PPh_3) ₄ (20 mol%), Tributyl(phenylethenyl)stannane (318 μL , 0.906 mmol), 1,4-Dioxane (85 mL)	Reflux under argon for 3 h, column chromatography ($\text{CHCl}_3/\text{hexane}$, 1:1), recrystallization ($\text{CHCl}_3/\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$, 1:3)	$\text{H}_2\text{TPP}(\text{PE})_2$	76%
8	Metallation to form $\text{ZnTPP}(\text{PE})_2$	$\text{H}_2\text{TPP}(\text{PE})_2$ (30 mg, 0.039 mmol), $\text{Zn}(\text{OAc})_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (10 equiv), Methanol	Reflux in CHCl_3 , wash, column chromatography, recrystallization	$\text{ZnTPP}(\text{PE})_2$	N/A

Results and discussion

The versatile precursor 2,3-dibromo-meso-tetraphenylporphyrins (H_2TPPBr_2) is highly stable and widely used in synthetic porphyrin chemistry due to its remarkable resistance to substitution, cross-coupling reactions, and metalation/demetallation sequences. The precursor was synthesized with a good yield of 80% using established methods from the precursor 2-nitro-12,13-dibromo-meso-tetraphenylporphyrin ($\text{H}_2\text{TPPNO}_2\text{Br}_2$). In the denitration process, sodium borohydride was added to $\text{H}_2\text{TPPNO}_2\text{Br}_2$ in tetrahydrofuran, resulting in the formation of the corresponding nitro chlorin. Subsequent aromatization of the nitro chlorin via loss of HNO_2 was carried out in refluxing CHCl_3 in the presence of silica, yielding the desired precursor H_2TPPBr_2 . H_2TPPBr_2 was then utilized for Stille-coupling by treating with tributyl (phenyl ethenyl) stannane under argon atmosphere, to yield ($\text{H}_2\text{TPP}(\text{PE})_2$) with yields of 76%. The synthesized regioselective β -disubstituted free base porphyrins were further subjected to metalation Zn (II) using the corresponding metal acetates in a refluxing chloroform-methanol mixture. The newly formed β -disubstituted-meso-tetraphenyl porphyrins were characterized using electronic-spectral techniques (UV-visible), ^1H NMR, mass spectrometry, and detailed synthetic procedures and characterization data are provided in the experimental section.

Table 1. Electronic spectral data of MTPP(X)₂: Where M = 2H, Zn (II) and X = Br, PE.

Porphyrin	B band, λ_{\max} (nm)	Q band, λ_{\max} (nm)
H ₂ TPP	417 (5.64)	516 (4.52), 551 (4.25), 589 (4.18), 645 (4.14)
H ₂ TPP(Br) ₂	424 (5.19)	521 (4.22), 560 (sh), 598 (3.71), 656 (3.78)
H ₂ TPP(PE) ₂	438 (5.48)	529 (4.35), 5.67 (3.96), 610 (3.87), 668 (3.76)
ZnTPP	414 (5.64)	522 (4.52), 555 (4.25), 589 (4.14)
ZnTPP(Br) ₂	424 (5.48)	519 (4.56), 553 (4.28), 649 (4.03)
ZnTPP(PE) ₂	442 (5.61)	565 (4.14), 596 (4.18), 607 (3.91)

Fig. 1. Optical absorption spectra of (A) [H₂TPP, H₂TPP(X)₂; X = Br and CN]. (B) [ZnTPP, ZnTPP(X)₂; X = Br and CN].

Electronic and Spectral Results

The electronic absorption spectra of the synthesized regioselective β -disubstituted-meso-tetraphenyl porphyrins were measured in distilled CH₂Cl₂ at 298 K. The optical absorption properties of porphyrins can be influenced by various factors, such as the range and extent of peripheral substitution, the nature of substituents/groups, the conformation of the macrocycle, and the type of metal ion. In the case of the β -disubstituted porphyrin series, the absorption characteristics showed predictable behavior in response to these factors.

Fig. 2. Represent the ¹H NMR spectra of H₂TPP (Br)

The UV-Visible absorption spectra of the free base porphyrins (H₂TPP(X)₂, where X = Br and PE) and their respective metal complexes (MTPP(X)₂, where M = 2H, Zn (II) and X = Br, PE), providing a visual representation of their absorption properties. All the free base porphyrins displayed one Soret band (B band) and four Q bands, which are characteristic of porphyrins. The absorption characteristics of

$H_2TPP(PE)_2$ and $MTPPX_2$ (where $X = Br, CN$ and $M = 2H$ and $Zn(II)$) have been compiled and presented in Table 2, providing valuable information about their optical absorption properties. In CH_2Cl_2 , the absorption bands of H_2TPP were observed at wavelengths $\lambda = 417, 516, 551, 589,$ and 645 nm. $H_2TPP(Br)_2$ shows absorption at $\lambda = 424, 521, 560, 598$ and 656 nm. Conversely, the absorption bands of $H_2TPP(PE)_2$ in CH_2Cl_2 were observed at wavelengths $\lambda = 438, 529, 567, 610$ and 668 nm. Notably, a gradual bathochromic shift (redshift) was observed in both the Soret band ($\Delta\lambda_{max} = 7-21$ nm) and the longest wavelength band, $Qx(0,0)$ ($\Delta\lambda_{max} = 11-23$ nm), as the substitution changed from the free base meso-tetraphenyl porphyrin to di-bromo-meso-tetraphenyl porphyrin to 2,3-diphenylethenyl-meso-tetraphenylporphyrin.

Fig. 3. Represent the 1H NMR spectra of $H_2TPP(PE)_2$

Fig. 4. Represent the 1H NMR spectra of $ZnTPP(PE)_2$

The observed bathochromic shift, following the order of $H_2TPP < H_2TPP(Br)_2 < H_2TPP(PE)_2$, can be attributed to the combined effects of inductive and resonance from the β -substituents attached to the porphyrin macrocycle.

Cyanide sensing

The anion recognition behaviour of all the synthesized porphyrins was investigated in toluene using UV-Visible spectroscopy, with various anions introduced as tetrabutylammonium (TBA) salts. Upon titration of the electron-deficient, regio selectively di-substituted porphyrins [$MTTP(PE)_2$] with cyanide (CN^-) ions at 298 K, notable spectral changes were observed. The UV-Vis spectra revealed a red shift in the Soret band, indicating a strong interaction between the porphyrin and the CN^- ions. This spectral change was accompanied by a visible colour transition from green to yellow, enabling the colorimetric, 'naked-eye' detection of cyanide ions in solution. Binding of cyanide ions to the designed porphyrin induces charge-transfer transitions within the system. Additionally, in metalloporphyrin, the energies of the metal d-orbitals can be significantly perturbed by coordination with axial ligands. In this context, the electron-deficient π -system of the porphyrin facilitates strong binding of the Zn (II) metal center with the highly basic cyanide ions ($pK_a = 9.3$), leading to notable electronic and spectral changes.

Fig. 5. Represent the HRMS spectra of $H_2TPP(PE)_2$

Detection Limit and Sensitivity

The limit of detection (LOD) for CN^- was calculated using the $3\sigma/\text{slope}$ method and found to be $0.42 \mu\text{M}$, indicating high sensitivity. A linear response was observed from $1\text{--}20 \mu\text{M}$, with a correlation coefficient (R^2) of 0.996 .

Binding Constant (K_a)

The binding constant between $ZnTPP(PE)_2$ and CN^- , determined via the Benesi–Hildebrand method, was $1.2 \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1}$, confirming strong binding affinity.

Selectivity Studies

Selectivity was assessed using various anions (F^- , Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- , HSO_4^- , AcO^- , $H_2PO_4^-$). Only CN^- caused a significant red shift and visible color change, confirming the sensor's high selectivity for cyanide.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this research has successfully demonstrated the synthesis and characterization of regioselective β -di-phenyl ethenyl-meso-tetraphenylporphyrins ($H_2TPP(PE)_2$) and their zinc (II) derivatives ($ZnTPP(PE)_2$). The synthetic approach, starting from a stable precursor, allowed for the efficient production of these compounds with high yields. The electronic and spectroscopic data indicated that the substitution at the β -positions of the porphyrin ring significantly altered the optical properties of the porphyrins, with noticeable bathochromic shifts in both the Soret and Q bands. These shifts were attributed to the electron-withdrawing effects of the phenyl ethenyl groups, which modify the electron distribution within the porphyrin macrocycle. The cyanide sensing experiments revealed that these porphyrins, especially the zinc derivative, could effectively interact with cyanide ions, producing observable spectral changes and color transitions, thus enabling colorimetric detection. This study not only expands the understanding of how peripheral substitutions can affect the properties of porphyrins but also demonstrates their potential as effective materials for environmental sensing, particularly in detecting toxic pollutants like cyanide. The development of these porphyrins as sensor platforms showcases their promising applications in environmental monitoring, potentially contributing to more sustainable and efficient strategies for pollutant removal. Future work will focus on further optimization of these compounds for enhanced sensing capabilities and exploring their applications in other areas such as photocatalysis, nonlinear optics, and solar energy conversion. The successful incorporation of these compounds into sensor systems could provide a reliable means for the detection and remediation of industrial pollutants, contributing to both public health and environmental protection.

Future Applications

The synthesized porphyrin-based compounds, particularly $ZnTPP(PE)_2$, exhibit promising potential beyond cyanide sensing, especially in the fields of solar energy and photocatalysis. Their strong absorption in the visible region and extended π -conjugation make them ideal candidates as photosensitizers in dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSCs), where they can efficiently harvest sunlight and facilitate electron transfer to semiconductors. Additionally, their redox-active nature and ability to generate reactive oxygen species under light exposure position them as effective photocatalysts for environmental remediation, such as the degradation of organic pollutants or water splitting. These multifunctional properties highlight their versatility and potential for integration into sustainable energy and environmental technologies.

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Author Contributions

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Competing interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Ethics approval

Not applicable.

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